

USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO STUDY ONLY BASAL SOUNDWAVES' EFFECTS ON EMG SIGNALS

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Abstract

Basal Soundwaves are the soundwaves in the laboratory room where the scientific study is conducted, and no generated sound or soundwaves are applied. Basal Soundwave (BS) is represented in Table 1 and figure 2 with the letter S which stands for silent sound, but this silence is not a complete absence of sound. There are three different Basal soundwaves (BS) in this scientific study and they include S-1, S-2 and S-3, and each of them is recorded in threes as follows: S-1 S-1 S-1, S-2 S-2 S-2 and S-3 S-3 S-3. It has been shown that human adults detect and hear sound within a frequency range of 20 Hz and 20 KHz or 20 Hz and 20,000 Hz, but that of infants is slightly higher than 20 KHz and decreases in sensitivity as they grow. And while ultrasound is a high frequency sound above 20, 000 Hz and consequently too high to be heard by humans, infrasound remains a low frequency sound below 20 Hz and consequently too low to be heard by humans. Soundwaves in peoples' rooms or environment could be detrimental or therapeutic hence the sound therapy practiced before antiquity by the Igbos, Australian Aborigines and the Egyptians. In fact, the therapeutic and detrimental effects of basal soundwaves are expressed as "uda juuu or juuu na-ajuli na ajunwukwa" in Igbo lingo and energy medical practices such as sunbaths, water-cleansing, earthing and air-baths during which calming or stimulating sounds are meditatively listened to for a prime purpose of all-encompassing healing. Uda juuu na-ajuli na ajunwukwa simply means "silent sound heals and kills"; and this killing part is in consonant with the detrimental health effects of infrasonic frequencies that impair respiratory system and cardiovascular system (L, 1998; Solecki L. , 2000; Solecki L. , 2010). The novelty of this article is not only the divulgence of basal soundwaves' effects on EMG signals using artificial intelligence, it is also a divulgence of a concise review of detrimental impacts of basal soundwaves on human health, enjoining people to be conscious of basal soundwaves in their environment as some of these soundwaves could be unhealthful. A balanced basal sound environment must be ensured in order to have a biological homeostasis called health, otherwise ill-health will ensue.

Keywords: Electromyography, EMG Signals, CleveLab Kit, MATLAB, Machine Learning, Basal Soundwaves, Sound Energy, Sound Therapy, Sunbaths, Water Cleansing, Earthing, Grounding, Air-baths, Sound Bath, Frequency, Amplitude, Frequency Medicine, Energy Medicine, Natural Sound Healing.

Aim: My objective is to build an artificial intelligence-based model for prediction of human muscle's response to only basal soundwaves. No generated soundwaves are applied.

Introductions

Sounds around people make direct impact on the people (arturel, 2024), and such sound effects could be healthful and unhealthful. Even when sleeping, the auditory system is constantly open receiving the sound waves in the environment (Spreng, 2000). Soundwaves had significant effects on human subjects according to the first scientific study on soundwaves' effects on EMG signals using artificial intelligence, and for the fact that muscle tissue is a vital component of virtually all body organs and systems, any positive or negative soundwaves' effects on the muscle can positively or negatively affect structural and functional activities of respiratory, reproductive, cardiovascular, endocrine, gastrointestinal, immune and nervous systems, and can extend similar influences to vision, energy metabolism, temperature regulation and general body homeostasis (Ozuomba & Z, 2025). Loud environmental soundwaves lead to annoyance, sleep disturbances, sleep problems, tinnitus, hearing impairment, hearing loss, cardiovascular problems and serious physical and mental health impairments (World Health Organization, 2018; Quebec, 2022; WHO, 2024). Human muscle is made up of cells (Braithwaite & Khalili., 2023; Bianconi, Piovesan, Facchin, & Beraud, 2013; Mostafa, 2021). Cell to environment interactions or cell

to cell interactions and communications through electromagnetic field (EMF) leave a long term effect on the functions of individual cells or a group of cells, and no matter how weak the interaction between a biological system and electromagnetic energy is, the interaction will still have the capacity to influence a developing system (Rouleau & Dotta, 2014).

Loud sounds can also instigate stress chain reactions in people's brain, resulting in secretion of stress hormone called cortisol which can negatively influence general wellbeing thereby increasing the people's chances of developing long-term health problems and complications, and if these affected people are exposed to a well-balanced sound environment with cool and relaxing sound wave energies, they get well again (Lim, et al., 2018). Additionally, while noisy sound disrupts concentration, causes sleep disturbances and attendant cardiovascular diseases, a well-balanced sound environment promotes quality of life and general wellbeing of the people (arturel, 2024); and this is called sound therapy (Heather, 2007) which is an ancient medical approach (Goldsby & Goldsby, 2020) that actually heals (Habibi & Damasio, 2014). The infinitely ancient people called the Igbos, apart from other energy medicines such sunbaths, water-cleansing, earthing/ground-

ing and air-baths that they extensively practiced listening meditatively to sounds of diverse pitches and amplitudes for major purpose of healing, they also availed themselves the inspirational essence of sound energy to amplify their scientific and technological know-hows deepening their knowledge of natural intelligence, afa diagnostic procedures, astronomy, astrology, four most basic states of matter and four cardinal points of East, West, North and South which represent Eke, Orié, Afó and Nkwuó with which they developed a 4 days per week system, 7 weeks per month system and 13 months per year system. Of crucial importance is meditative use of sounds for healing during new moons the actual new months, equinoxes and solstices called *Onwaohuru*, *Ọdaomumu* and *Omumu* in Igbo lingo and during veneration of Chukwu. The Igbos also utilize healing sound energies during celebrations of one’s maternal and paternal genetic essence called Chi, during celebration of sub-energies of Chi called *Onyeuwa* and *Ágù*, during celebration of one’s genealogical entities called *Ndichie*, *Ndiokpu na Ndiegede*, during celebration of one’s infinite propelling force called *Ikenga*, during celebration of one’s infinite creative powers called *Agwu*. One of the ancient sanctuaries called *Uhu-Nneagwu* where *Agwu* or *Ezumezuagwu* is individually or communally acknowledged and celebrated with healing sound energies still exists at *Umueshi-ahuruike*, *Amokwu*, *Ezemeazu*, *Uruala*. Furthermore, sound energy healing was not only witnessed during natural energy healing practices at *Nssude pyramids*, it was also used as incentives and motivations to Igbo iron smelters at *Lejja* part of *Enugwu* (Ozuomba, 2025).

Materials

1. CleveLab system with five snap electrodes for numerical and graphical EMG data collection.
2. MATLAB was used to build the artificial intelligence model (AI Model).
3. Healthy Volunteers who underwent the electrography studies that provided me with numerical data with which I used to build the AI model.

Method

Attached to bicep and wrist extensor muscles of each volunteer are snap electrodes, and attached to elbow bone of each of them is also snap electrodes to record the effects of the basal soundwaves on their EMG signals. The healthy volunteers underwent electromyography (EMG) studies in a laboratory room with basal soundwaves 1, 2 and 3 (BS=S-1 Hz, BS=S-2 Hz and BS=S-3 Hz).

Recording was done three times during BS=S-1 Hz, BS=S-2 Hz and BS=S-3 Hz in a CleveLab system with five snap electrodes to get both graphical and numerical data. However, it is only the numerical data that I used to build the Artificial Intelligence (AI) Model. Each recording lasted for 5 seconds. I used the classification method with MATLAB Tools---Classification Learner for the machine learning model. Note that I first preprocessed, and analyzed the numerical data in Microsoft Excel before I proceeded to train the model with different statistical methods in MATLAB software.

RESULTS

The Artificial Intelligence (AI) model that I built with numerical data of the electromyography and trained it with different statistical methods in MATLAB software showed different accuracy. And the best of the accuracy results was gotten with Ensemble Bagged Trees (75%). The muscles’ response to the basal soundwaves S-1 and S-3 showed a False Negative Rate of 100% while the muscles’ response to S-2 showed a True Positive Rate of 100%. In other words, studying the effects of only the basal soundwaves on human muscle separately showed 75% accuracy, true positive response strength of 100% in S-2 and false negative response rate of 100% according to the AI model that I built. It is important to note that hidden features and information about the EMG data were not detected manually but with artificial intelligence.

Table 1

Basal Soundwaves = Silence Soundwaves

<i>BS = S-1 (Hz)</i>	<i>BS = S-2 (Hz)</i>	<i>BS = S-3 (Hz)</i>
1	2	3
1	2	3
1	2	3

Figure 1. True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Negative Rate (FNR)

Figure 2. True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Negative Rate (FNR)

Conclusion

Results of this scientific study show that human muscles have a strong response of 100% to basal soundwaves when studied alone. The outcomes of the AI Model, apart from detecting distinctions in the EMG data, they also show that human muscle responds and reacts to basal soundwaves strongly and differently.

Humans, even when in a quiet room or in an environment with basal soundwaves, adsorb, absorb and can adapt to the soundwaves without even knowing it. Environmental basal soundwaves can impact human body healthfully or un-healthfully since muscle is a vital a components of virtually all body organs and systems where they play both functional and structural roles for general wellbeing. Energy medicine including sound

healing could be a possible augmentation or replacement for certain conventional medical treatment and procedures. Considering all these realities, I encourage more evidence based studies on energy medicine particularly on soundwaves or basal soundwaves effects on human health as more indulgences in these studies will help predict and/or detect more potent and effective therapeutic sound frequencies and amplitudes for healing of mankind in particular and the universe at large.

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